

RTBV and RTSV incidence on TKM6 and TN1 at different days after transplanting. IRRRI, 1987 WS.

indexed by ELISA for the presence of RTBV and RTSV.

In 1987, at 92 DT (when TN1 had 100% infection with both RTBV and RTSV), TKM6 had 69% infection with RTBV only (see figure). In the 1988 trial, when tungro incidence was relatively lower, RTBV incidence on

IR20 was 0.6% at 14 DT and increased to 2.6% at 55 DT. Very low infection with both RTBV and RTSV and no infection with RTSV alone were recorded.

Infectivity test of green leafhopper (GLH) collected at 44 DT from IR20 plots yielded a low percentage of

Infectivity on TN1 seedlings of GLH collected 44 DT from field plots planted to IR20 and TN1. IRRRI, 1988 WS.

Source of GLH	GLH tested (no.)	GLH transmitted (%)		
		RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV
IR20	129	0.01	0.01	0
TN1	132	42	13	2

infective leafhoppers; GLH collected from an adjacent field planted to TN1 with 30% tungro incidence had high infectivity (see table).

Because transmission of RTBV by GLH depends on the presence of RTSV, RTBV incidence will not increase remarkably nor become RTBV + RTSV if the population of RTSV-infected or RTBV + RTSV-infected plants is very low. □

Bacterial blight (BB) resistance in some Nepal rice cultivars

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We evaluated nine traditional and two improved rices reported resistant to BB in Nepal in the greenhouse at IRRRI

against Philippine races of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*. Plants were clip-inoculated at maximum tillering with inoculum (10^8 CFU/ml) from each race group. Lesion development was measured on 10 randomly inoculated leaves of each cultivar 14 d after inoculation.

Reaction to the races varied significantly among cultivars (see table).

Rato anadi was highly resistant to races 2 and 5, Saeto anadi was resistant only to race 5. Laxmi was moderately resistant to races 1, 4, and 5. In general, the Nepalese rices had low levels of resistance to the Philippine races of *X. c* pv. *oryzae*. □

Reaction of some Nepalese rice cultivars to 6 Philippine races of *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae*. IRRRI, 1989.

Cultivar	Lesion length ^a (cm)						Mean
	1 (PXO61)	2 (PXO86)	3 (PXO79)	4 (PXO71)	5 (PXO112)	6 (PXO99)	
Ghaiya	5.14 c	10.40 bc	7.21 c	19.41 b	6.42 c	35.65 a	14.04 bc
Saeto anadi	27.48 a	26.54 ab	16.70 b	23.57 ab	1.35 c	25.21 ab	20.14 a
Rato anadi	18.06 bc	1.24 d	12.61 c	23.03 ab	1.08 d	28.87 a	14.15 bc
Choto marshi	21.89 a-c	11.87 c	12.91 bc	22.93 ab	17.56 bc	30.15 a	19.55 a
Ramdulari	18.68 b	20.88 ab	12.99 b	18.90 b	14.11 b	30.45 a	19.34 a
Malbhog	12.27 b	9.04 b	8.89 b	10.79 b	12.70 b	28.68 a	13.73 bc
Gadar	12.69 bc	22.42 a	8.74 c	8.48 c	21.67 b	32.93 a	17.82 ab
Sataraj	14.63 ab	11.67 ab	7.40 b	18.17 a	14.77 ab	18.55 a	14.20 bc
Jaswa	16.31 bc	25.18 ab	16.51 bc	13.67 c	13.25 c	28.95 a	18.98 a
Janaki ^b	10.07 b	20.72 a	8.66 b	8.76 b	5.53 b	11.84 ab	10.93 c
Laxmi ^b	4.86 b	18.13 a	9.94 ab	6.62 b	4.10 b	17.62 a	10.21 c
TN1	22.56 b	21.24 b	17.02 b	23.91 ab	7.04 c	32.89 a	20.78 a
Mean	15.39 bc	16.61 b	11.63 cd	16.52 b	9.96 d	26.81 a	16.15

^aDisease was assessed by lesion length: 0.0-3.0 cm = resistant, 3.1-7 cm = moderately resistant, 7.1-10.0 cm = moderately susceptible, 10.1 cm or longer = susceptible. In a row, means having a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bImproved cultivar.

Insect resistance

Screening rice varieties for damage caused by *Oebalus insularis* (Stål)

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In 1985, insect pests and diseases affected about 50% of the rice area in Cuba. The pests that caused the greatest damage were water weevil and stink bug. *O. insularis* is the most plentiful and widespread bug species. Use of resistant varieties plays an important role in widely accepted integrated control.